

PRACTICES AND PREPARATIONS ON INTERNATIONALIZATION: A CASE OF SOUTH COTABATO, SARANGGANI, AND GENERAL SANTOS

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Practices and Preparations on Internationalization: A Case of South Cotabato, Sarangani, and General Santos

Sadam M. Musa, * Shirmae L. Abison, Erlinda G. Haudar, Melanie N. Gulmatico
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

In the era of internationalization, Philippine higher education institutions (HEIs) are compelled to continually refine their operations and governance to align with global standards. This descriptive cross-sectional survey research was conducted to assess the extent of practices and preparations for internationalization at a state university in SOCCSKSARGEN, Philippines. The study engaged seven administrators and eighteen faculty members as respondents, collectively offering a perspective on the university's approach to internationalization. The study reveals that the university has initiated practices and preparations geared towards internationalization. Furthermore, it is evident that there is a need for further enhancement of its strategic directions and plans to more comprehensively integrate internationalization into its academic programs, policies, and administrative processes. This paradigm shift will require a measured, time-sensitive approach to ensure that the university achieves its internationalization objectives effectively. To expedite this process, the university administration could proactively take the lead in championing and facilitating internationalization efforts. This proactive leadership is pivotal in building a culture of global engagement, forging international partnerships, and positioning the university as a frontrunner in the international academic landscape. By doing so, the university can more effectively embrace the challenges and opportunities of internationalization in higher education.

Keywords: *practices, internationalization, global standards, globalization, philippines*

Introduction

The rise of globalization and the growing interconnection of economies and societies, the academic community's internalization plays a vital role. It works the cultural exchanges and equips students for a future becoming more fluid (Grad & Van der Zande, et al. 2022). The implementation of policies and strategies that enable the incorporation of international perspective, experiences, and collaborations into the fundamental operation of higher education institutions including teaching, research, outreach, and production.

The Philippines, situated in Southeast Asia has actively engaged in regional integration through its membership in the association of Southeast Asia Nations. The integration has presented various opportunities and challenges, prompting Philippine to adapt to the evolving demands of a changing educational environment (Zuhain, et al 2020). The progression of Association of Southeast Asia Nation integrations essential for competitive and technologically adept human capital. The higher education institution are compelled to shift their focus towards equipping students with the necessary skills to meet the evolving demands by integration. The higher education institution must engage in continuous innovation and strategic restructuring to proactively address the emerging challenges of the 21st century (Bautista et al , 2021).

This universities are urged to surpass and engage in a continuous process of self-improvement. The universities must acknowledge the shift from the information age to the age of insights. The focus of this study center on a specific university in SOCSARGEN Universities in the Philippines, and its initiatives in internalization. The universities dedicated to academic excellence, acknowledges the importance of competitiveness globally. Therefore, this study aims to explore the practices and preparations undertaken by this universities as it progresses towards internalization.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the universities preparedness and internalization practices, specifically to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. position;
 - 1.3. academic rank; and
 - 1.4. department?
2. What is the extent of practice in terms of:
 - 2.1. curriculum and instruction;
 - 2.2. research collaboration;
 - 2.3. academic standards and quality;
 - 2.4. mobility and exchanges for students and teachers;
 - 2.5. international and intercultural understanding networking;
 - 2.6. cooperation and development assistance;

- 2.7. international students' recruitment;
- 2.8. facilities and support system; and
- 2.9. income generation?

3. What are the preparation of the Universities towards internalization?

Literature Review

Curriculum Development

This underscores the importance of a holistic approach to internationalization, encompassing curriculum development, resource allocation, and collaborative initiatives. The university offers programs in various modalities, allowing students from different countries to access courses at their convenience, supported by information and communication technologies for efficient learning, receiving a relatively positive rating. A higher score in this aspect aligns with the inclusive nature of internationalization, emphasizing diversity and accessibility.

Moreover, the institution's initiative in developing joint curriculum programs with foreign institutions/universities is notable, essential for maintaining global educational relevance. Regular updates to the syllabus reflect the dynamic nature of internationalization, ensuring students are equipped to tackle evolving global challenges (Egitim, 2022).

While the institution moderately scores in courses that promote cross-cultural understanding and appreciation and in creating joint programs with foreign partners, there is recognition of the importance of tailored education to meet diverse stakeholder needs (Ansell et al., 2022). Customized programs play a crucial role in addressing unique educational requirements locally and internationally.

On the other hand, the university's inclusive curriculum receives a moderate rating, indicating adaptability to accommodate students from diverse backgrounds. Flexible learning approaches support educational accessibility across borders (Talosa et al., 2021; Ulanday et al., 2021). However, the lower score suggests a need to enhance special learning experiences that foster cultural appreciation among different tribal groups or races.

Research Collaboration

The university involves faculty, students, and administrative staff in international studies as researchers, conducting research on international comparative education to explore differences among nations. The high mean score reflects a proactive approach to driving international research endeavors, showcasing the institution's commitment to global engagement and knowledge creation. Furthermore, the university organizes international conferences to present and disseminate research studies, contributing to the global knowledge pool. This underscores the institution's positive impact on the international academic landscape and its role in advancing global scholarship (Chankseliani et al., 2021). On the other hand, the involvement of university faculty, students, or administrative staff in international studies as respondents received a moderate rating, indicating room for further engagement in this aspect.

Conversely, the institution's leadership in research activities conducted in collaboration with educational institutions or industries in other countries received the lowest mean score. Despite this, the university's focus on research in international comparative education to comprehend global educational differences remains significant. Comparative studies play a crucial role in providing insights into internationalization and educational diversity (Phan et al., 2019).

Academic Standard and quality

The institution demonstrates a commitment to academic excellence. The university actively benchmarks its curricular and extra-curricular activities with national and international standards. This high mean score indicates a strong commitment to aligning its programs with recognized quality benchmarks. Benchmarking with standards demonstrates a commitment to maintaining and improving academic quality (Goodwin, 2021; Tsiligiris & Hill, 2021). The institution also has faculty and administrators with high profiles, recognized for their expertise both locally and abroad. The result suggests a commitment to building a team of recognized experts. High-profile faculty and administrators contribute to the institution's academic reputation and can attract students and collaborations. On the other hand, the institution has reached level three accreditation by a nationally known accrediting body. This suggests a commitment to meeting national quality standards. Justification: Accreditation is an essential indicator of academic quality and accountability.

Mobility and Exchange of Students and Teachers

The institution has students studying in other institutions abroad for some of their courses delivered online or face-to-face. This suggests that the university is involved in student mobility. Student mobility fosters international exposure and cross-cultural experiences. Further, the university has international students studying on-campus or online. This indicates a certain level of international student presence. Attracting international students contributes to diversity and cultural exchange (Gao & Liu, 2020; Zhu, 2019).

The institution actively engages in Memorandum of Agreements or Understandings with institutions from other countries for international or intercultural understanding/networking. This relatively high mean score suggests a proactive approach to international partnerships and networking. Such agreements foster international collaboration and understanding. The university has twinning

programs with foreign institutions, indicating a moderate level of collaboration. Twinning programs provide opportunities for students and faculty to engage in international educational experiences (Anthap pan, 2022). On the other hand, the institution has a Center for Multicultural Education or Foreign Students Organization. Having such centers indicates a commitment to cultural understanding. These centers serve as hubs for intercultural learning and support for international students. The university has accredited international students' organizations. Accreditation indicates recognition and support for these organizations. Accredited international students' organizations facilitate international and intercultural understanding.

The institution actively participates in international academic networks/alliances, consortia, or links with other universities and colleges in other countries. This relatively high mean score suggests a strong commitment to international academic partnerships. Engagement in academic networks builds collaboration and knowledge exchange. The university is also involved in formulating policies to achieve ties with other colleges/universities in ASEAN or NGOs on education. This score indicates a commitment to shaping policies for international collaboration. Policy formulation supports strategic cooperation in education and development (Miranda et al., 2021). Meanwhile, the lowest mean was found in the indicator that the university offers scholarships/grants for international students from less developed countries in ASEAN ($M=1.95$). While this score is lower, offering financial support for international students signifies a commitment to accessibility. Scholarships/grants contribute to international student recruitment and inclusivity.

The institution has educational programs, course offerings, syllabi, and policies for admission and retention of students available online. The finding suggests that the university provides some online information regarding educational programs. Online availability of program information is essential for prospective international students' access. The institution has a responsive system to address inquiries from prospective international students. This suggests a commitment to addressing inquiries promptly. Prompt responses to inquiries are crucial for attracting and retaining international students.

The university provides medical and dental support for its local and foreign faculty members, staff, and students. This signifies the availability of healthcare services. Healthcare support contributes to the well-being of the university community. The university has its library with a convergence of complete and updated materials and facilities, both print and non-print. This score indicates a commitment to maintaining a well equipped library. A well-stocked and updated library is crucial for academic excellence. The institution has provisions for guidance and counseling for international students. This suggests a commitment to supporting the well-being of international students. Guidance and counseling services are essential for the academic and personal development of students.

The institution is committed to exploring alternative income sources and engaging in income generating projects in collaboration with foreign agencies or institutions. While there is room for improvement, the university's commitment to financial sustainability and income diversification is evident. The university has income-generating projects (IGP) in partnership with foreign agencies or institutions. This indicates a commitment to income generation through projects in collaboration with foreign entities. Collaborative income-generating projects enhance financial stability. Also, the institution generates alternative sources of income by offering educational programs or creating publications patronized by international institutions and industries. This suggests that the university explores alternative income sources. Diversifying income sources contributes to financial sustainability.

Methodology

Research Design

The research applied a descriptive survey research design utilizing a survey questionnaire as the primary instrument for data gathering. A descriptive survey research design is a methodology employed to gather, analyze, and interpret data to depict the attributes of a population or phenomena. This approach focuses on evaluating and without aiming to establish causal relationships. The descriptive survey method was utilized to ascertain how respondents articulate the extent of the University's practices and preparedness for internationalization.

Respondents

The respondents of the study was regular employees of the Universities in the South Cotabato, Sarangani, and General Santos faculty, administrator in the Department of CIT, CAS, and CHS. The twenty five (25) respondents were comprehensively chosen as the respondents of the study. These were composed of seven administrators, and eighteen (18) faculty members of a State University's in SOCKSARGEN as chosen respondents of the study.

Instruments

The researcher employed adapted from the Rubric on Internalization of Teacher Education developed by the Balagtas, et al (2012) and served as the primary tool for data collection. This was designed in a Likert Scale format. It comprises of two parts: the first section includes the demographic profile of the respondents information, while the second section focuses on practices towards internalization aligned with the crucial dimensions of internalization. Padama et al.(2010) established a framework that encompasses these nine key dimensions, the curriculum and instruction, facilities and support systems cooperation and development Assistance, Diversified Income generation, Research Collaboration, International and Intercultural Understanding/Networking Academic Standard and quality, Mobility and Exchanges for students and Teachers, and Internalization Students Recruitment.

The modified tool's third section included an open-ended question regarding preparedness for internalization.

Procedure

The researcher prepared a letter and reviewed by the member of the panels, and send a permission letter to conduct at the chosen institutions to the President of the University's, administrators, and faculty of the chosen school respondents. The permission generally obtained from the Campus Director and program chairs of the three department. The survey questionnaires were administered, and selected respondents were interviewed.

Ethical Considerations

This research study followed standard ethical guidelines. The respondents participated willingly. Care was taken to ensure their safety and wellbeing and that they suffered no physical, mental, social, or emotional harm. There was always respect for the school head and stakeholders who took part. The confidentiality of the data gathered.

Results and Discussion

As shown in Table 1 revealed the sex distribution shows that 40.00% of the respondents were male, while 60% were female. Then, majority of the respondents were faculty members of the University's accounting for 72% with 28% being administrators' respondent. Given the study's focus on internationalization, centering on the faculty perspectives as they play a direct role in the academic aspects of this process. In terms of academic rank, instructor was the highest percentage of 48%, followed by the Associated Professor with a percentage of 32%, Assistant Professor 12%, and full Professor was 8%. In terms of the Department profile of the respondents, the highest percentage was College of Arts and Sciences (CAS) 48%, the College of Industrial Technology (CIT) 32%, then the lowest percentage was College of Health Science was 20%.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	10	40%
Female	15	60%
Total	25	100%
Position		
Faculty	18	72%
Administrator	7	28%
Total	25	100%
Academic Rank		
Instructor	12	48%
Assistant Professor	3	12%
Associate Professor	8	32%
Full Professor	2	8%
Total	25	100%
Department		
CIT	8	32%
CAS	12	48%
CHS	5	20%
Total	25	100%

Responses of the Respondents in Terms of the Extent of Practices on Curriculum and Instruction.

Table 2. Responses of the Respondents in Terms of the Extent of Practices on Curriculum and Instruction

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. The institution has an inclusive curriculum	3.13	0.73	Evident
2. It has courses in foreign languages to understand the people of other countries.	2.56	0.90	Evident
3. It offers courses that may serve as a venue for understanding and appreciation of other countries' culture.	2.84	0.92	Evident
4. It has customized programs responsive to the demands of different sectors, agencies, or organizations here and abroad.	3.00	0.63	Evident
5. It has programs delivered in different modalities that could allow students from other countries to take course at their own time and place.	2.58	0.81	Evident
6. It has information and communication technologies that could facilitate efficient and effective learning.	2.72	0.83	Evident
7. It has its own laboratory to test theories or theorize from experiences.	2.88	0.71	Evident
8. It provides the students with special learning experiences where they could appreciate the culture of other tribal groups/classes or races.	2.88	0.77	Evident
9. It has created a joint curriculum or course program with foreign institutions/universities.	2.52	0.75	Evident

10. It regularly updates the syllabus of course offerings to integrate the new trends and address pressing global issues that have implications to education.	3.04	0.82	Evident
Section Mean	2.81	0.82	Evident

Legend: 1-49 Not Evident 1.50-2.49 Slightly Evident 2.50-3.49 Evident 3.50-4.49 Very Evident

Table 2 revealed the responses of the respondents in terms of the extent of practices on curriculum and instruction. The highest mean was item number One, the institution has an inclusive curriculum with the mean of 3.13 at the standard deviation of 0.73 described as “Evident”. Then followed by the item number ten, it regularly updates the syllabus of course offerings to integrate the new trends and address pressing global issues that have implications to education with the mean of 3.04 with the standard deviation of 0.82 described as “Evident”. Then item number 4, It has customized programs responsive to the demands of different sectors, agencies, or organizations here and abroad with the mean of 3.00 with the standard deviation of 0.63 described as “Evident”. Then the lowest mean was item number 9, It has created a joint curriculum or course program with foreign institutions/universities with the mean of 2.52 at the standard deviation of 0.75 as described “Evident”. All in all of the indicators with the section mean of 2.81 with the standard deviation of 0.82 described as “Evident”. This implies that Commission of Higher Education in the Philippines were always updated and followed the agreement between the UNESCO.

Responses of the Respondents in Terms of the Extent of State University’s Practices on Research Collaboration

Table 3 revealed the highest mean among the indicators were item number 1, the institution leads research activities done in collaboration with educational institution or industries in other countries with the mean of 3.24 with the Standard Deviation of 0.76 described as “Evident”. The item number 10 was the second to the highest mean of 2.92 with Standard Deviation of 0.70 describe “Evident”, and item number 2 stated that it has faculty, students or administrative staff who participate in international studies as researchers with a mean of 2.84 with the standard deviation of 0.92 described as “Evident”. Among the six indicators, the lowest mean was item number 4 stated that It conducts studies on international comparative education to understand differences between and among nations with a mean value of 2.56 with standard deviation of 1.04 described as “Evident”. The over all section mean was 2.83 with standard deviation of 0.89 described as “Evident”. It implied that Universities in SOCKSARGEN were doing their task on research both local and international studies manifesting evident.

Table 3. Responses of the Respondents in Terms of the Extent of State University’s Practices on Research Collaboration

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. The institution leads research activities done in collaboration with educational institution or industries in other countries.	3.24	0.76	Evident
2. It has faculty, students, or administrative staff who participate in international studies as researchers.	2.84	0.92	Evident
3. It has faculty, students, or administrative staff who participate in international studies as respondents.	2.72	0.96	Evident
4. It conducts studies on international comparative education to understand differences between and among nations.	2.58	1.04	Evident
5. It organizes international conferences where research students are presented or disseminated.	2.75	0.97	Evident
6. It contributes to the growing body of knowledge recognized abroad.	2.92	0.70	Evident
Section Mean	2.83	0.89	Evident

Legend: 1-49 Not Evident 1.50-2.49 Slightly Evident 2.50-3.49 Evident 3.50-4.49 Very Evident

Responses of the Respondents in Terms of the State University’s Extent of Practice in academic Standards and Quality

Table 4 revealed the highest mean was item number 2 stated that, it benchmarks its curricular or extracurricular activities with national and international standards with a mean of 3.00 with the standard deviation of 0.63 described “Evident”, then item number 4 with a mean of 2.96 with standard deviation of 0.77 described as “Evident” that faculty and administrators with high profile, and third one was item 5 and 7 with a mean of 2.92 with a standard deviation of 0.89 described “Evident” consecutively. Further, the seven indicators, the lowest mean was 2.56 with the standard deviation of 0.70 described as “Evident”, and ovel all mean was 2.84 with standard deviation of 0.83 described as “Evident”. It implied that quality and academic standard manifested evident and teachers were doing their best in teaching.

Table 4. Responses of the Respondents in Terms of the State University’s Extent of Practice in academic Standards and Quality

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. The institution has reached level three accreditation by a nationally known accrediting body.	2.88	0.86	Evident
2. It benchmarks its curricular or extra-curricular activities with national and international standards.	3.00	0.63	Evident
3. It has become the benchmark of other institution.	2.56	0.70	Evident
4. It has faculty and administrators with high profile	2.96	0.77	Evident
5. It has faculty, administrators and staff with special training or exposure abroad.	2.92	0.89	Evident
6. It is recognized in international society.	2.67	0.90	Evident
7. It has faculty and administrators who received grant abroad, scholarship.	2.92	0.89	Evident
Section Mean	2.84	0.83	Evident

Legend: 1-49 Not Evident 1.50-2.49 Slightly Evident 2.50-3.49 Evident 3.50-4.49 Very Evident

Responses of the Respondents in Terms of State University’s Extent of Practice in Mobility and exchanges for Students and Teachers.

Table 5 revealed the highest mean of 2.44 with a standard deviation of 0.98 described as “Slightly Evident” stated that the institution has students studying in other institutions abroad for some of their course delivered online or face to face. Then, followed by the item number 5 stated that, it has visiting professors from other countries who do academic work in the institution with the mean of 2.36 with the standard deviation of 1.13 described as “Slightly Evident”, then item number 2 stated that the has foreign students studying in the institution taught online or face to face with a mean of 2.24 with the standard deviation of 0.95 described as “Slightly Evident”. The lowest mean was 1.96 with the standard deviation of 1.08 described “Slightly Evident”. Over all mean for five indicators were 2.50 with standard deviation of 1.03 described “Evident”. It implied that manifesting exchanges of students and teachers international was the evident school meet the standard and quality of education.

Table 5. *Responses of the Respondents in Terms of State University’s Extent of Practice in Mobility and exchanges for Students and Teachers*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. The institution has students studying in other institutions abroad for some of their course delivered online or face to face.	2.44	0.98	Slightly Evident
2. It has foreign students studying in the institution taught online or face to face.	2.24	0.95	Slightly Evident
3. It has faculty members who taught abroad for faculty exchange programs or served as consultants abroad.	2.00	1.02	Slightly Evident
4. It has faculty from foreign institutions who are teaching some courses for the students of the institution.	1.96	1.08	Slightly Evident
5. It has visiting professors from other counties who do academic work in the institution.	2.36	1.13	Slightly Evident
Section Mean	2.50	1.03	Evident

Legend: 1-49 Not Evident 1.50-2.49 Slightly Evident 2.50-3.49 Evident 3.50-4.49 Very Evident

Responses of the Respondents in Terms of State University’s Extent of Practice International and Intercultural Understanding/ networking.

Table 6 revealed that the highest mean was 2.91 with standard deviation of 1.02 described as “Evident” that the institution has memorandum of agreements or memorandum of understanding with institutions from other countries for any international or intercultural understanding/networking. Then, item number 3 participates in international assemblies or activities to promote one’s culture with a mean value of 2.74 with standard deviation of 0.74 described as “Evident”, and the item number 4 organizes both curricular and or extra-curricular multicultural activities with a mean of 2.70 with the standard deviation of 0.75 described as “Evident”. Further, seven indicators, the lowest mean was 2.09 with the standard deviation of 0.93 described as “Slightly Evident” the faculty, students, or administrative staff are active members of international organizations. As gleaned from the table, the practices of the state university towards internalization in terms of intercultural understanding/networking are slightly Evident, as revealed by the weighted mean of 2.40 with the standard deviation of 1.00. This indicates that the states university is moderately engaged in international and intercultural understanding / networking.

Table 6. *Responses of the Respondents in Terms of State University’s Extent of Practice International and Intercultural Understanding/ networking*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. The institution has memorandum of agreements or memorandum of understanding with institutions from other countries for any international or intercultural understanding/networking.	2.91	1.02	Evident
2. It has twinning programs with foreign institutions.	2.52	0.97	Evident
3. It participates in international assemblies or activities to promote one’s culture.	2.74	0.74	Evident
4. It organizes both curricular and/ or extra-curricular multicultural activities.	2.70	0.75	Evident
5. Its faculty, students, or administrative staff are active members of international organizations.	2.41	0.94	Slightly Evident
6. It has a center for multicultural education/foreign students organization that serves as a venue for understanding the culture of different nations.	2.09	0.93	Slightly Evident
7. It has accredited foreign students’ organizations.	1.91	0.93	Slightly Evident
Section Mean	2.40	1.00	Slightly Evident

Legend: 1-49 Not Evident 1.50-2.49 Slightly Evident 2.50-3.49 Evident 3.50-4.49 Very Evident

Responses of the Respondents in Terms of State University’s Extent of Practice on Cooperation and Development Assistance.

Table 7 revealed the highest mean value was item number 1, the institution is engaged in international academic networks/alliances, consortia or link with other universities ad colleges in other countries with the mean of 2.74 with the standard deviation of 0.79 described as “Evident”. Then, followed by the item number 2, it is engaged in formulating policies to achieve academic, scientific, economic, technological, or cultural ties with other colleges/universities in ASEAN or NGOs education with a mean of 2.61 with the standard deviation of 0.82 described as “Evident”. The third one was item number 3 with a mean value of 2.45 with the standard deviation of 0.89 described as “Slightly Evident” in terms of receives funding for the promotion of cultural understanding/international

learning/ecumenical or inter-religious activities. Further, the lowest mean was item number 6, it offers scholarships/grants for foreign students who come from less developed counties in ASEAN. The section mean was 2.29 with standard deviation 0.93 described as “Slightly Evident”. This suggests that the state university is moderately engaged in cooperation and development assistance. The lowest mean was found in the indicator that the university offer scholarships/grants for international students from less developed countries in ASEAN.

Table 7. *Responses of the Respondents in Terms of State University’s Extent of Practice on Cooperation and Development Assistance*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1.	The institution is engaged in international academic networks/alliances, consortia, or link with other universities and colleges in other countries.	2.74	0.79	Evident
2.	It is engaged in formulating policies to achieve academic, scientific, economic, technological, or cultural ties with other colleges/ universities in ASEAN or NGOs on education.	2.61	0.82	Evident
3.	It receives funding for the promotion of cultural understanding/international learning/ ecumenical or inter-religious activities.	2.45	0.89	Slightly Evident
4.	It has international development projects commissioned by ASEAN and international agencies.	2.18	0.89	Slightly Evident
5.	It opens its programs to foreign students from ASEAN less developed countries that have satisfied the entry requirements.	2.30	0.91	Slightly Evident
6.	It offers scholarships/grants for foreign students who come from less developed countries in ASEAN.	1.95	0.88	Slightly Evident
Section Mean		2.29	0.93	Slightly Evident

Legend: 1-49 Not Evident 1.50-2.49 Slightly Evident 2.50-3.49 Evident 3.50-4.49 Very Evident

Responses of the Respondents in Terms of State university’s Extent of Practice on International Students’ Recruitment.

Table 8 revealed the extent of practice on International Students’ Recruitment, the highest mean was item number 1, the institution has educational programs course offerings, syllabi, and policies for admission and retention of students available online with the mean value of 2.17 with the standard deviation of 1.01 described as “Slightly Evident”, then followed by the item number 3, it has a responsive system to address inquiries of prospective foreign students with the mean value of 2.00 with the standard deviation of 0.83 described as “Slightly Evident”, and the lowest mean was item number 2, it has a responsive computerized or online system for recruiting, screening, and enrolling international students with the mean value of 1.87 with the standard deviation of 0.85 described as “Slightly Evident”. The section mean of 2.25 (SD=0.92) implies that the state university is moderately engaged in practices related to international students’ recruitment. While there are variations in scores, the university demonstrates a commitment in providing online information and responsive systems.

Table 8. *Responses of the Respondents in Terms of State university’s Extent of Practice on International Students’ Recruitment.*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1.	The institution has educational programs, course offerings, syllabi, and policies for admission and retention of students available online.	2.17	1.01	Slightly Evident
2.	It has a responsive computerized or online system for recruiting, screening, and enrolling international students.	1.87	0.85	Slightly Evidence
3.	It has a responsive system to address inquiries of prospective foreign students.	2.00	0.83	Slightly Evidence
Section Mean		2.25	0.92	Slightly Evidence

Legend: 1-49 Not Evident 1.50-2.49 Slightly Evident 2.50-3.49 Evident 3.50-4.49 Very Evident

Responses of the Respondents in Terms of State University’s Extent of Practice in Facilities and Support System.

Table 9 revealed the highest mean value on the extent of practice in facilities and support system, the item number 3, it has sufficient number of licensed full-time librarians in all its sections with the mean value of 2.67 with the standard deviation of 0.69 described as “Evident”. Then followed by the item number 6, it provides medical and dental support for its local and foreign faculty members staff, and students.

Table 9. *Responses of the Respondents in Terms of State University’s Extent of Practice in Facilities and Support System*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1.	The institution has classrooms equipped with state of the art technologies.	2.50	0.87	Evident
2.	It has its own library with the convergence of complete and up-dated materials/facilities, both print and non-print.	2.54	0.96	Evident
3.	It has sufficient number of licensed full-time librarians in all its sections.	2.67	0.69	Evident
4.	It has a dormitory with complete amenities for local and foreign students.	2.50	0.76	Evident
5.	It has provision for guidance and counseling of foreign students.	2.54	0.82	Evident
6.	It provides medical and dental support for its local and foreign faculty members, staff, and students.	2.63	0.81	Evident
7.	It has amenities/support systems for its foreign students, faculty, and visitors.	2.50	0.87	Evident
Section Mean		2.42	0.87	Slightly Evident

Legend: 1-49 Not Evident 1.50-2.49 Slightly Evident 2.50-3.49 Evident 3.50-4.49 Very Evident

Then, third one was the item number 2 and 5 with the mean of 2.54 and Standard Deviation of 0.96, 0.82 consecutively described as “Evident” that, it has its own library with the convergence of complete and up-dated materials/facilities both print and non-print; it has provision for guidance and counseling of foreign students. Further, the lowest mean was item number 1 and 7 with the mean value of 2.50 with SD=0.87 described as “Evident”. These were indicates, that the institution has classrooms equipped with state of the art technologies, and it has amenities/support systems for its foreign students, faculty, and visitors. The section mean 2.42 (SD=0.87) described as “Slightly Evident” implies that the university can further improve its practices towards internalization. The results indicates that the state university is moderately engaged in providing facilities and support systems.

Responses of the Respondents in Terms of the State University’s Extent of diversity income generation

As gleaned from the table 10, the practices of the state university towards internalization in terms of diversity income generation are slightly evident, as revealed by the weighted mean of 2.43 and standard deviation of 0.84. This indicates that the state university is moderately engaged I diversity income generation. Further, the highest mean among the three indicators was item number 2, it has income generation projects in partnership with foreign agencies or institutions and industries with the mean value of 2.23 (SD=0.90) described as “Slightly Evident”; then the lowest mean was item number 3, it has a specific budget coming from its partners educational institutions from other countries with the mean of 2.09 (SD=0.79) described as “Slightly Evident”.

Table 10. Responses of the Respondents in Terms of the State University’s Extent of diversity income generation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. The institution generates alternative sources of income, like offering educational programs or creating publications patronized by international institutions and industries.	2.18	0.78	Slightly Evident
2. It has income-generating projects in partnership with foreign agencies or institutions.	2.23	0.90	Slightly Evident
3. It has a specific budget coming from its partner educational institutions from other countries.	2.09	0.79	Slightly Evident
Section Mean	2.43	0.84	Slightly Evident

Legend: 1-49 Not Evident 1.50-2.49 Slightly Evident 2.50-3.49 Evident 3.50-4.49 Very Evident

Summary of the State University’s Practices towards Internalization

Table 11, the practices of the university towards internationalization are evident, as revealed by the weighted mean of 2.53 and a standard deviation of 0.90. It indicates a moderately strong commitment to internationalization efforts. While some aspects excel (academic standards and research collaboration), others may require further attention and improvement (international students’ recruitment and cooperation and development assistance). The state university excels in academic standards and quality (M=2.84), ranking first among all aspects. This indicates the institution’s commitment to maintaining high academic standards and ensuring the quality of its programs. High academic standards are essential for international recognition and the quality of education (Madani, 2019). The university also demonstrates a strong focus on research collaboration (M=2.83), ranking second among all aspects. This signifies active engagement in collaborative research activities, vital for knowledge exchange and international recognition. Research collaboration enhances the in situation’s global reputation and knowledge contribution (Varghese, 2022). The State University places significant emphasis on curriculum and instruction, ranking third among all dimensions (M=2.821). This highlights the institution’s commitment to providing inclusive and quality education. A strong curriculum is fundamental for internationalization efforts.

Table 11. Summary of the State University’s Practices towards Internalization

Aspect	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Rank
Curriculum and Instruction	2.81	0.82	Evident	
Research Collaboration	2.83	0.89	Evident	
Academic Standards and Quality	2.84	0.83	Evident	
Mobility and Exchanges for students and teachers.	2.50	1.03	Evident	
International and intercultural understanding/networking	2.40	1.00	Slightly Evident	
Cooperation and development assistance	2.29	0.93	Slightly Evident	
International students’ recruitment	2.25	0.92	Slightly Evident	
Facilities and support system	2.42	0.87	Slightly Evident	
Diversity income generation	2.43	0.84	Slightly Evident	
Overall Mean	2.53	0.90	Evident	

Legend: 1-49 Not Evident 1.50-2.49 Slightly Evident 2.50-3.49 Evident 3.50-4.49 Very Evident

Moreover, the university ranks fourth in the aspect of mobility and exchanges for students and teachers (M=2.50). This suggests a commitment to providing opportunities for international experiences. Promoting mobility and exchanges supports a diverse and global learning environment. The university places fifth in diversity income generation, reflecting a commitment to exploring alternative income sources (M=2.43). Diverse income sources contribute to financial sustainability, which is essential for internationalization. The institution ranks sixth in facilities and support systems, focusing on providing necessary facilities and services (M=2.42). Quality facilities and support are crucial for enhancing the overall educational experience. Also, the university ranks seventh in international and intercultural understanding/networking (M=2.40). This suggests room for improvement in fostering international relationships and cultural understanding. Enhancing international and intercultural understanding is pivotal for global engagement. The state university ranks eighth in cooperation and development assistance, indicating a need for further collaboration and support (M=2.29). Collaboration and development assistance are essential for internationalization efforts and growth. The university ranks ninth in

international students' recruitment, suggesting opportunities for improvement in this area ($M=2.25$). Effective recruitment is essential for attracting a diverse student population.

Analysis of the Preparations Towards Internalization of the State University in the SOCSKSARGEN

In the table 12, the respondents cited several ways that need to be considered in the university's preparations for internationalization. The conduct of capability-building activities underscores the importance of enhancing the competencies of faculty and staff through specialized training and professional development. By offering these activities, the university can equip its personnel with the knowledge and skills necessary to engage with international programs and standards. This is crucial for maintaining the academic quality and relevance of the institution in a global context. The provision of state-of-the-art facilities emphasizes the need for upgrading the university's facilities, particularly laboratories, to meet international standards. State-of-the-art facilities are essential for research, practical training, and creating an environment conducive to international collaboration. Providing modern facilities can enhance the institution's competitiveness and appeal to both local and international students and researchers (Bamberger et al., 2020). The strengthening of faculty and student exchange programs highlights the importance of faculty and student exchange programs as a means to strengthen international exposure and collaboration. Sending faculty and students abroad promotes cross-cultural understanding, facilitates knowledge transfer, and helps establish international partnerships (Li & Zhu, 2019). This approach contributes to a more diverse and globally connected academic community. Lastly, the utilization of ICT-based information delivery underscores the role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in internationalization efforts. Leveraging ICT for communication, information sharing, and networking is crucial in establishing connections within the ASEAN Region and beyond. ICT facilitates collaboration, knowledge exchange, and access to global resources, contributing to the university's internationalization objectives (Al-Agtash & Khadra, 2019).

Table 12. Analysis of the Preparations Towards Internalization of the State University in the SOCSKSARGEN

Theme	Significant Statement Description
Preparations towards Internationalization of the State University in SOCSKSARGEN.	The university administrators were needed to conduct capability-building, aside from the provision of state-of-the-art facilities. These are the specialSpecial training, seminar courses, and other related professional development activities for faculty and staff on specific programs. The university must exert more effort to improve the current status of its laboratories and facilities.
The integration of ICT in the management and development of the state universities.Provision of state-of-the-art facilities	The teachers respondents revealed that the utilization of ICT-based information delivery. The university must exert more effort to improve the current status of its laboratories and facilities.These are the approaches of the state universities in how technology contributes effectively to the different aspects or operations of the universities.
The coping mechanisms of the state universities in the SOCSKSARGEN.	The respondents revealed that school administrators should be strengthening the faculty and student exchange program. This is the best coping mechanism to address the immediate need of the universities, which is the main goal of internationalization.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that:

The university actively engages in various dimensions of internationalization, strongly focusing on academic standards, research collaboration, and curriculum and instruction. While there are areas for improvement, the institution's overall commitment to internationalization is evident, aiming to create a more inclusive and globally connected learning environment. There is clear evidence that further improvement is needed in refining its strategic directions and plans to fully integrate internationalization into its academic programs, policies, and administrative processes.

This transformative shift requires a well-paced, time-sensitive approach to ensure the successful realization of the university's internationalization objectives.

The preparations must be given adequate time to ensure the attainment of targets. To expedite this process, the university administration should take a proactive stance in spearheading and facilitating internationalization initiatives. This proactive leadership is crucial in nurturing a culture of global engagement, establishing international partnerships, and positioning the university as a leader in the global academic landscape. Through these actions, the university can better embrace the challenges and opportunities presented by internationalization in higher education.

Further, the institution is encouraged to conduct a regular replication of the study every three years. This approach will allow the institution to consistently evaluate its progress in terms of internationalization, identify its strengths, and pinpoint areas needing improvement. These periodic assessments will enable the institution to adapt and enhance its strategies effectively in pursuing global engagement.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Sadam M. Musa

Lambayong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Shirmae L. Abison

General Santos City National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Erlinda G. Haudar

Kalamansig National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Melanie N. Gulmatico

Koronadal Central Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines